

Newsletter n°2 – November 2023

HORIZON EUROPE Programme GA No. 101057404

Welcome to the second ZDZW project newsletter!

After a year the **ZDZW** project began, many events have taken place: numerous participations in important international fairs and conferences, several scientific publications, four plenary meetings, and countless consortium meetings to establish synergies that allow us to achieve the ambitious objectives of this project. If you want to **know more about what has happened in the last 6 months** within the **ZDZW** project, keep reading!

Our community is growing every day, but we still miss you. Don't miss this newsletter to **know how the ZDZW project can contribute to your manufacturing processes** and become one of the few companies able to **test our inspection solutions!**

More info is available on the website (www.zdzw-project.eu).

ZDZW in a Nutshell

6
Use cases across different industrial sectors & processes

11
Non-destructive inspection solutions for process monitoring and control

27
Partners

11
Countries

12
Industrial Partners

36
months

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Participate in the ZDZW Open Beta Testing Pilot!

Would you like to reduce waste and defects in your manufacturing process?

Dive into the ZDZW Project Beta Testing campaign and learn all the benefits it offers to your manufacturing process!

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ACCESS TO BETA TEST UP TO 11 INSPECTION SOLUTIONS DEVELOPED BY LEADING INDUSTRY PLAYERS ACROSS EUROPE

Watch the [ZDZW Open Beta Testing Pilot video](#)

- FREE TESTING**
- PERSONALISED OFFER**
- 7% INCREASE YOUR PRODUCTIVITY**
- 25% DECREASE IN ENERGY CONSUMPTION**
- 50% REDUCTION IN MATERIAL WASTE**

What inspection solutions will you have at your disposal?

1. Volumetric Inspector

To work in the production line, capturing images in **real time** without requiring reconfiguration.

2. Surface Anomaly Detector

With a 3D Camera and AI algorithms to **ensure the quality** on the production and **identify visual defects**.

3. Mechanical Hardness Inspector

Real-time inspection based on **Digital TWIN** to define the microstructural and hardness evolution during induction heat treatments.

4. AE-Based Integrity Assessment

Acoustic emissions-based integrity assessment to **predicts** in an early stage the **quality** of the product and **anticipates** possible **defects** arising during its manufacturing process.

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5. Welding Process Monitoring

Online welding defect detector which allows to estimate the presence of defects during the welding with AI analysis.

6. MIR-OCT

Real-time, non-contact, and non-destructive inspection with ultra-high-resolution images to reduce defect-related delays and energy waste.

8. EMAT UT

Ultrasonic-based system for in-line multi-pass weld inspection with defect characterization.

7. Heat Transfer Digital Twin

Thermoforming Digital Twin to help thermoformed plastic part manufacturers to reduce raw material & energy consumptions thanks to its optimization algorithm and defect prevention capability.

9. Artificial Vision

An edge AI machine vision inspection device to identify visual defects on manufactured goods, checking correct assembly and preventing the inclusion of faulty pieces in the final product.

10. IR Thermal Imaging

Real-time data in 4D and control every step of heat-sealing process as a accurate system to detect defects in thermal imaging.

AR-Enhanced Inspector to locate and visualize defects on large-scale system by inspecting the whole target object via augmented reality with a hand-held device.

11. AR-Enhanced Inspector

All this and more information is available on the [ZDZW website!](https://www.zdzw-project.eu)

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What is happening in the ZDZW project?

5 Conference publications

12 Events [fairs, conferences, workshops]

Scientific publications

CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS

CLEO EU Conference

Mid-infrared OCT for non-destructive sub-surface inspection and in-line production monitoring [Article]
June 2023

CLEO EU Conference

MIR Supercontinuum Using Gain-Switched and Modelocked Pumping [Poster]
June 2023

Optica Nonlinear Optics Topical Meeting

Supercontinuum noise reduction with short normal dispersion fibers – a simple and general technique [Article]
July 2023

CIO 2023 Conference

Non-Destructive inspection solutions in the EU industrial sector for sustainable manufacturing [Article/Poster]
July 2023

PRO-VE 2023

Collaborative Network for the development of Non-Destructive Inspection Technologies: Elicitation requirements in an industrial environment [Article/Poster]
July 2023

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What is happening in the ZDZW project?

Events

Participation in the 23rd Manufacturing Congress
25-27/10/2023

Participation in A&T – Automation & Testing Fair
26/10/2023

Participation in the 21st European Week of Regions and Cities
12/10/2023

4th Plenary meeting in Darmstadt
17-19/10/2023

MATTCH webinar organized by FBA to present ZDZW solutions
20/09/2023

Participation in 24th IFIP/Socolnet Working Conference on Virtual Enterprises PROVE 2023
27-29/09/2023

Participation in EFFRA Manufacturing partnership day
26/09/2023

Participation in the Optical Nonlinear Optics Topical Meeting
10-13/07/2023

Participation in CIO 2023 Conference
6-7/07/2023

Advisory group meeting
27/06/2023

Organization of digitalization, sustainability and people day by GRI
21/06/2023

Participation in CLEO/Europe-EQEC 2023
27/06/2023

Participation in Eurada digitalisation working group
25/05/2023

Participation in Maintenance fair 2023
06-08/06/2023

Participation in Made in Steel 2023, conference and exhibition for the steel industry
09/05/2023

Participation in SPS 2023 - Smart production solutions.
23/05/2023

3rd plenary meeting in Valencia after DMIS
28/04/2023

Co-organizers of DMIS - Digital Manufacturing Industrial Summit 2023
25-27/04/2023

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Publications in the ZDZW COMMUNITY

ikerlan
MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

The ZDZW approach for Zero-Waste Manufacturing

- Does the concept of "Zero Defect Manufacturing" ring a bell?
- Are you curious how to get the most out of this idea to boost your productivity?

Containerisation as a tool for interoperability

- The Containerisation concept
- Containerisation in the ZDZW project approach
- Kubernetes: the leader technology in container orchestration.
- Helm/Rancher package manager for Kubernetes

Revolutionizing Manufacturing: Automated 3D Vision Systems for Zero Defects

- What is the significance of industrial inspection for manufacturing competitiveness, and what are the challenges with current visual inspection processes?
- How does the new vision inspection technology overcome these challenges?
- How does an automated vision system contribute to achieving zero defects?

Sustainability assessment tools for zero defect and zero waste manufacturing practices

- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA),
- Life cycle cost (LCC)
- Social Impact Assessment (SIA)

Join the ZDZW community to keep you up to date with the ZDZW project evolution!

ZERO DEFECT WASTE

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